

Investigation on Pond Culture Fish Species in Relation to Pond System of Zarthapyin Area, Hpa-An Township, Kayin State

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Abstract

Fish culture in pond system has been identified as one of the important income generating activities. This study was carried out in Zarthapyin area, Hpa-an Township, Kayin State. A total number of fish specimen in fish pond were recorded from this area. In this study systematic position, description, type of feed, good pond construction, liming, control system of aquatic vegetation, water quality, type of fish pond and size, fish feeding, fertilization, type of soil, fish culture system, production cost, preparation for transport, transportation were recorded. Interview surveys were conducted to DOF officers as well as farm owners to record the socioeconomic conditions of the rearing fish species.

Introduction

Fish is the basic main food for Myanmar people where it is available in every part of States and Regions in Myanmar. Myanmar people prefer to eat fish especially fresh water fish than marine or brackish water fishes. Fish can be cultured in marine, brackish or freshwater. Depending on the facilities designed to serve as enclosures in rearing, fish can be grow in earthen ponds, concrete tanks, cages, pens, or run-ways (DOF, 2014). In 2010-2011 Fiscal year, the total production of fish was 4.4 million metric tons in Myanmar (DOF, 2011).

The Union of Myanmar possessed the very rich aquatic resources as the long three coastal regions namely Rakhine, Ayeyarwaddy and Tanintharyi and inland water bodies including Long river and wet Lands. At the other hand, brackish water areas such as Ayeyarwaddy delta region is also advantage for the rich of resources and biodiversity.

The main objectives of present study were

- To investigate the species composition in pond culture fishes
- To mention the descriptive characters of recorded species
- To know about the pond construction and managements

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Zarthapyin area, Hpa-an Township, Kayin State. Fishery Station and Winner Land group of fish pond (Latitude 16°36'32.22" N and Longitude 97°42'59.49" E).

Fig. 1 Map of study area (Source – Google earth)

Study Period

December 2019 to December 2020.

Use of Material

Boat, Net and truck are used for carrying and feeding, to harvest and to transport.

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Data Collection

Data was collected through interviews guided. The relative data was obtained from DOF officers as well as farm owners. The collected specimen was carried out by plastic box and taking available photographs for the study.

Identification

The systematic position of studied fish was followed after Day(1878), Nelson(1976), Talwar and Jhingran(1991).

Results

A total of six species, belonging to six genera, five families and four orders were recorded from Zarthapyin area.

Systematic position of pond culture fishes

Phylum	-	Chordata
Class	-	Actinopterygii
Order	-	Perciformes
Family	-	Cichlidae
Genus	-	<i>Oreochromis</i>
Species	-	<i>O. niloticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Order	-	Characiformes
Family	-	Serrasalminidae
Genus	-	<i>Piaractus</i>
Species	-	<i>P. branchyomus</i> (G. Cuvier, 1818)
Order	-	Siluriformes
Family	-	Pangasiidae
Genus	-	<i>Pangasianodon</i>
Species	-	<i>P. hypophthalmus</i> (Sauvage, 1878)
Family	-	Clariidae
Genus	-	<i>Clarias</i>
Species	-	<i>C. macrocephalus</i> (Gunther, 1864)
Order	-	Cypriniformes
Family	-	Cyprinidae
Genus	-	<i>Labeo</i>
Species	-	<i>L. rohita</i> (Hamilton & Buchanan, 1822)
Genus	-	<i>Puntius</i>
Species	-	<i>P. gonionotus</i> (Bleeker, 1850)

Species Description

***Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Common name - Nile Tilapia

Local name - Tilarpia

Length – 30cm, Weight – 0.35 kg

Well-breed animal. Small head, tail profile, foot ball shape, bluish-gray color, light vertical stripes. Caudal fin with regular dark and vertical stripes. Dorsal fin with dark margin. Typically higher number of dorsal spines. Diurnal feeding pattern. Omnivorous, primarily copepods, hydra, insects and phytoplankton. Freshwater fish, second most widely cultured in the world.

Habitat – Found in freshwater and brackish water.

***Piaractus brachyomus* (G. Cuvier, 1818)**

Common name - Red bellied pacu

Local name - Yae cho nga moat

Length – 30 cm, Weight – 2.5 kg

Can and will grow quickly under favourable conditions. Strong and robust fish need a lot of swimming space. Herbivorous species, feeding on fruits, nuts, and seeds. Also take insects, zooplankton and small fish. Possesses powerful dentition that can cause serious bites. Important food fish.

Habitat – Distribution South America: Amazon and Orinoco River basins, Myanmar.

***Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* (Sauvage, 1878)**

Common name - Striped Catfish

Local name - Nga dan

Length – 52 cm, Weight – 3 kg

Common aquaculture species. Freshwater habitat. The species is a large, found relatively slow growing catfish. Omnivore, feeding primarily on algae, plants, zooplankton, insects, fruits, crustaceans, and fish. Maximum life span is estimated 20 years.

Habitat – Cambodia, Lao, Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar.

***Claris macrocephalus* (Gunther, 1864)**

Common name - Bighead catfish

Local name - Nga khu

Length – 35 cm, Weight – 0.25 kg

Elongate body that is broader at the head; tapering toward the tail. Four pair of barbells. Pectoral spines are large and robust and finely serrated along the margins. Dorsal, caudal and anal fins together form a near-continuous margin. Found in a variety of habitat, most commonly encountered in muddy or swamp.

Habitat – In Southeastern Asian and throughout the most of Florida.

***Labeo rohita* (Hamilton & Buchanan, 1822)**

Common name - Carp, rohu

Local name - Nga myit chin

Length – 52 cm, Weight – 2.5 kg

Fresh water fish. Snout bluntly projecting, no lateral lobe; lips rather thick; barbels two, silvery. Colour bluish or brownish above; some scales on sides with red center and the fins are black.

Habitat – Distribution in sind, cutch and from Punjab through India and Assam to Myanmar.

***Puntius gonionotus* (Bleeker, 1850)**

Common name - Tarpian

Local name - Nga-kone-ma

Length – 30 cm, Weight – 0.7 kg

Body is deep and strongly compressed. The back is elevated and dorsal profile arched. Color when fresh is silvery white, sometime with a golden tint.

Habitat – Found at midwater to bottom depths in rivers, streams, floodplains, and occasionally in reservoirs.

Preparation for transport

Fishes are either netted early in morning or Late evening as the additional Stress imposed by high daytime temperature can severely affect survival. The most convenient method is to net the fish in the Late evening condition placed over night and pack and distribute early the following morning.

Transportation

Most of fry and fish products were transported to fish market and villages by truck.

Pond Culture System

Good Pond Construction

Earthen Ponds: These are selected by enough clay-content to hold water and then digging soil in a carefully selected site for construction. Where the soil structure is weak to retain adequate water, dug out earthen ponds can be rain forced with concrete for fish culture. Pond depth is between (5 to 7) feet and less than 6 feet increases the chances of aquatic vegetation problems. Shallow ponds tend to be more productive, but ponds that are too shallow suffer the risk of dying under summer drought.

Liming

All study ponds with soft and acidic water. Sometime required the addition of lime to improve fishing. The amount of lime is used 1-50 bags in each pond per year depending on soil pH. The cow dung compost were placed on the base of the pond for supplementary feed and will assist in binding the soil and making it less to water loss.

Control System of Aquatic Vegetation

Aquatic plants was controlled by pulling, cutting, digging or moving. The grass carp is the most effective long term control for aquatic plants. Plants densities is greater than 30% can caused fish kills.

Water quality

Stream Water or rain water was used. Water quality in pH level is between 6.5 to 9. Water clarity should be at least 18 inches throughout the year and is necessary for plankton production. Rain water is main sources of water. A good water source will be free of salt and clay, aquatic insects, potential predators and toxic substances and if will have high concentration of dissolved oxygen. If the source of water contains toxic materials can either kill fish directly or accumulate in fish body which smells and brings harm to people's health.

Type of fish pond and size

Ponds were constructed as quadrilateral form for all culture system. This is easiest to build and manage. The scale size is between 0.01 to 3.0 Acre.

Fish culture system

Polyculture system, three species, four species were mixed reared.

Type of soil

Soil with 20% to 35% clay are the best for building ponds. The mud bottom type is the most productive.

Fertilization

Water fertility determines a ponds productivity. Fertilizer increases pond productivity by stimulation the growth of microscopic plants. Fertilization makes the water turn green, shading the bottom and preventing growth of nuisance aquatic plants. Once fertilization is start, it should be continued. Aquatic plants supply oxygen, provide cover and can be food for insects that are eaten by the fish.

Type of feed

Three kinds of feed such as rice bran, peanut cake and pellet were recorded. Rice bran and pellet were fed as major feed in all culture system. Feeding was done twice a day in each pond.

Fish feeding

All ponds produce some natural food for fish but sometimes not enough to really get the fish.

Production Cost

Production rate in ton, income in million kyats, were based on rearing area. Investment included the purchasement of fry and or fingerling, labor cost, pond preparation, purchasement of lime and food.

Percentage of recorded species by Order

Discussion

In the present study a total of six species, six genera and five families under five orders were recorded. Two species of Cypriniformes and Siluriformes, One species of Characiformes and one species of Perciformes were observed. Due to the data Cypriniformes and Siluriformes are the largest orders and Perciformes and Characiformes are the smallest order. Pond condition greatly affect fish growth and fish yield. Under favourable conditions, the yield may be 2 or 3 times higher than in ponds. The 3 species poly culture ponds that got the most profit were constructed quadrilateral form. During the pond preparation lime was introduced systematically into the pond to kill the harmful bacteria and to bloom the phytoplankton for fish nutrition.

Moreover four species polyculture can cause the insufficient food supply caused by the crowded condition which can also cause to decrease the growth rate for rearing fish species. The basic earthen pond design system is still the most important affordable type of design and remains mostly unchanged and still highly relevant in less developed countries (Basudha.Ch, et al, 2019). The site should be close to the road for proper transportation of fish to market and also the transportation of inputs like feeds, fertilizers and construction material at the site.

The quality of water source must be examined. If the source contains toxic materials can either kill fish directly. Production rate in ton, income in million kyats, were calculated based on rearing area.

Rearing periods are determined by local conditions, climate, culturing methods and market demand. Pond condition greatly affect fish growth and fish yield. Yield may be 2 or 3 times higher than in ponds. Poly culture facilitate full utilization of the natural food organisms and vegetable plants in the pond water so production is maximized.

Conclusion

The fish production was found to the highest profitable income. The fries and fingerline were obtained during the harvesting period. Moreover, four species poly culture can cause the insufficient to the food supply caused the crowded condition and decrease also the growth rate for rearing fish species. Present study observed a total of six species, six genera, five families and four orders were recorded. These species are *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Piaractus brachypomus*, *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*, *Claris macrocephalus*, *Labeo rohita* and *Puntius gonionotus*. Production rate in ton, income in million kyats were based on rearing area.

Three species and four species polyculture system were observed in study period. The three species polyculture ponds got the most profit. Lime was introduced systematically into the pond to kill the harmful bacteria and to bloom, the phytoplankton for the fish nutrition. Soil with 20% to 35% clay are the best for building pond. The mud bottom type is the most productive. Rain water or Stream water was used and pH level is between 6.5 to 9. Ponds were constructed as quadrilateral form for all culture system. The scale between 0.01 to 3.0 Acre. Aquatic plants was controlled by pulling, cutting, digging, or moving. The grass carp is the most effective long term control for aquatic plants. Plants densities is greater than 30% can caused fish kills. Most of fry and fish products were transported to fish market and villages by trucks. Polyculture facilitates full utilization of the natural food organisms and vegetable plants in the pond water. Fish production can be greatly increased through polyculture of various species with different feeding habits. Because of rearing polyculture, the natural food organisms and natural vegetation are fully utilized and production is mixed.

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